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СЕМАНТИКА ЛЕКСИЧЕСКОЙ ЕДИНИЦЫ С ПОЗИЦИЙ СИНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО ПОДХОДА

SEMANTICS OF LEXICAL UNIT IN SYNERGETIC PERSPECTIVE

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В статье исследуется развитие значения лексической единицы в русле синергетического подхода. Отмечено, что синергетическая лингвистика трактует язык как сложную, открытую, динамическую систему, активно взаимодействующую с окружающим миром на основе принципов порядка и хаоса, самоорганизации, бифуркаций. Эти же принципы лежат в основе взаимодействия подсистем внутри языковой системы. В центре настоящего исследования находится лексическая подсистема языка. Проведённый анализ развития системы значений лексической единицы показывает, что новое значение, появляющееся в результате взаимодействия двух источников, оказывается более сложным и не сводимым к простой сумме значений исходных единиц, то есть имеет синергетическую природу.

The article investigates the development of a lexical unit's meaning from the perspective of synergetic approach. It is noted that synergetic linguistics interprets language as a complex, open, dynamic system that actively interacts with the surrounding world based on the principles of order and chaos, self-organization, bifurcations. The same principles underpin the interaction of subsystems within linguistic system. The present research is focused on the lexical subsystem of the language. The analysis of the development of a lexical unit's system of meanings has shown that a new meaning, which appears as a result of liaison of two sources, turns out to be more complicated and not equal to the sum of initial meanings, therefore it is synergetic in nature.

Ключевые слова: синергетическая лингвистика, синергетическая система, семантическая система, концепт, метонимический перенос, концептуальная метафора, бифуркация, терминология.

Key words: synergetic linguistics, synergetic system, semantic system, concept, metonymical transfer, conceptual metaphor, bifurcation, terminology.

S ynergetic linguistics looks upon the language as an open, dynamic, self-organizing system. Synergetics (derived from Greek *synergeia* meaning ‘collaboration, co-action, complicity’) is an interdisciplinary field of scientific research, within which general laws of transition processes from chaos to order and conversely (processes of self-organizing and spontaneous disorgan-

izing) in open non-linear systems of physical, chemical, biological, ecological, social and other nature are studied [5].

The language demonstrates all the basic features and properties of a synergetic system:

- it is open to influences and impacts of the environment, both physical and social;
- it is dynamic, as it is changing and developing permanently;
- it is self-organizing, which is revealed in selectiveness of including various units into the language system, and in other processes;
- its nonlinearity is reflected in such linguistic notions, as syntagmatics and paradigmatics, explicitness and implicitness.

The concept of synergy implies that combined action of two or more phenomena produces effect greater than just a sum of the initial effects. This is commonly illustrated by the formula: $2+2=5$. In many cases such combined effect is not only greater but also quite new and cannot be seen as merely derived from the original phenomena. This synergetic effect can be observed in different subsystems or layers of the language. "In all times, the most intensively changing endo-system of any language was lexical macro-system, which has constantly been enriching with new naming units...". It is explained by the fact that lexical system is "the most open" to the exchange of substance, energy, and information with the environment surrounding a certain language" [2, p. 420].

Synergetic linguistics views the very origin of the language as the result of synergetic interaction between the human being and the environment. In the historic process of adaptation to the environment the first people had to create a flexible, reliable, and universal means of communication and cognition. We agree with the opinion that "a language has been formed spontaneously" but not completely "regardless of the will of man" [4, p. 4717]. Of course, the appearance of language was not a purposefully thought-over, conscious action but it seems obvious that at some period of interaction with the environment the ancient human felt vital need in more perfect communication tool in order to deal with various tasks and problems while adapting to surrounding conditions. The answer to this vital necessity was emergence of the language.

To operate with the objects and phenomena of the world it was necessary to name all those objects and phenomena. And the act of nomination, in its turn, is also a synergistic act: when a certain object acquires a name, i.e. two things (an object and its name), are linked, a far more essential and complicated mental formation is produced – a concept. "A concept is a constituent of thought or generalized idea, that designates common properties and characteristics abstracted from a number of instances. ... Human beings understand the world by applying concepts and expressing them with language" [9]. The name of one concrete thing now can be applied to a lot of similar things, consequently categorizing and classifying them. The concept, on the one hand, distinguishes the most significant features of this object that differentiate it from other objects, and, on the other hand, it links the object with a lot of different concepts on the basis of various relations – similarity, difference, opposition, etc.

The meaning of a linguistic unit is a synergetic system, as it usually consists of a number of components and it is in constant change, development, open to enlargement. This can be traced in the evolution of meanings of a word, for instance 'tree'.

The English word *tree* originates from the Proto-Indo-European root *dreu-* meaning 'firm, solid, steadfast' that acquired a specialized sense of 'wood, tree' [12]. In Old Germanic languages the word was used to denote a large plant with a strong stem and branches but this concrete meaning was deduced from a broader sense. Some scholars argue that ancient Germanic people used this word even in more specific sense – 'oak', as oak was the most typical plant of this kind for them. The earliest example of *tree* in the Oxford English Dictionary (with the plural *treeo*) is from the Vespasian Psalter, an illuminated manuscript dated **around 825** [11].

The idea of a strong upright trunk as the main feature of a tree was used to nominate an object of this form with the same word, so the meaning of the word ‘a pole, post, beam, bar, handle’ appeared. This was also employed to mean ‘gallows’. Further on the cross on which Christ was crucified was also named with the word ‘tree’.

Those were the meanings that were, so to say, materially connected with the original one, i.e. they denoted things made of wood and/or having the main structural element of a tree – the trunk. They were derived by metonymical transfer. Metonymy being an associative transfer of meaning is a synergetic process, as it is based on affinity of two different semantic domains, and the resulting effect is not equal to the sum of their features.

Innovative meanings emerge at points of bifurcation – points of branching in the line of a system’s enlargement and development. Noteworthy is that the very process of a system’s development is often metaphorically presented as a tree growth: a point on the trunk where a new branch appears symbolizes bifurcation, where the system finds a new way of development and thus transfers to a qualitatively novel state. In the case of the semantic structure of the word *tree* the stage of bifurcation, at which metonymical meanings were formed, resulted in the creation of a subsystem of meanings of this kind, open to further enlargement.

Another bifurcation led to the appearance of figurative meanings denoting something resembling a tree in form. Thus, the sense ‘family tree’ was first attested in 1706 [13]. Later this meaning was broadened to “a branching diagrammatic representation of something” [7]. These meanings bear the marks of conceptual metaphorization. A conceptual metaphor is understanding one domain of experience (that is typically abstract) in terms of another (that is typically concrete) [3, p. 13]. So nominating a drawing that shows relations between members of a family, or any related objects, with the word *tree* that has no material connection to it, while perceiving this drawing as having the main line (like a trunk) with minor lines coming from it (like branches) is obviously the process of semantic mapping of some elements and relations of the source domain – ‘tree’ to the target domain – ‘diagram’. As one of the basic archetypes of human cognition the concept of tree is employed in various fields of mental reasoning.

In this way interaction between the surrounding world and the language with interchange of information, momentum and energy results in creation and expansion of conceptual structure and the system of lexical meanings.

In the 18th century the word *tree* became a part of biological terminology. Tree species and their names are a product of a two-part plant naming system that was introduced and promoted by **Carolus Linnaeus** in 1753 [11]. Linnaeus’ classification made the unit *tree* a significant element of the scientific conceptual system with its definition that reflects the cognitive links of this concept with the system of related concepts: “A **tree** is the tallest form of plant floral diversity that is generally perennial, woody, and branched among other plant varieties” [10]. Terminological units *floral diversity*, *perennial*, *plant varieties* signal that the lexeme *tree* is a constituent of a specialized network of scientific concepts.

Metaphorical meaning of *tree* was used in other scientific and professional terminologies: in chemistry as “a treelike crystal growth; dendrite” [8], in computing as “a structure for organizing or classifying data in which every item can be traced to a single origin through a unique path” [6].

The bifurcation point, at which the word *tree* was included to a special sub-system – scientific language, turned it into a term, and by this led to a qualitatively new state of the semantic system.

Present-day cognitive terminological studies define the term as a verbalized scientific and technical knowledge [1, p. 30]. Many terminological units are borrowed from common use language by re-interpreting the meaning and applying it for special purposes. Language for special purposes (LSP) is understood as a special system within a language, its sub-system. LSP is created on the basis of the language of common use and borrows its lexical and syntactical bases adapting them to principal functions and features of scientific communication [1, p. 14].

Synergetic approach gives a deeper insight into linguistic processes, into the nature of meaning and semantic development. It presents semantic system as an open dynamic formation organized on the basis of synergy with the outer conditions and inner factors, and this synergy facilitates permanent enlargement and replenishment.

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